

TRANSLATION TRANSFORMATION AND CONTACT OF LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

The article points out that the types of translation transformations directly depend on the language characteristics (relatives or relatives, similar and different aspects of the language, i.e. typological aspects), the proximity of vocabulary to many or fewer uses of transformations, the closeness of vocabulary, and some other linguistic and extralinguistic factors.

Key words: differences, language contacts, linguistic factor, non-linguistic (extralinguistic) factor, related languages, similarities, translation transformations, translator's mastery., typological features.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/1dwj7z29>

The use of transformations in the translation process depends typologically on whether languages are close to or far from each other—the level of their relativeness. The translator determines which type of translation transformations to use. However, the translator does not think he will use this translation transformation. He chooses translation transformations intuitively, based on his own experience. Theoretically, it is possible to analyze translation transformations separately. In practical terms, in most cases, translation transformations come in mixed. Pure and specific transformational structures are widely used to interpret non-translatable words, translate particular words, and translate stylistic methods with stylistic expressive characteristics. The appropriate and efficient application of translation transformations is a characteristic of experienced and skilled translators. This does not mean that young translators do not have such an opportunity.

The types of translation transformation are selected based on the typological, stylistic, linguistic, pragmatic, lingua pragmatic, lingua cultural, and sociolinguistic characteristics of the two languages that have been contacted in connection with translation.

English belonging to the German family is one of the richest languages in the world. English is the official language of the five largest countries in the world— Great Britain, the United States, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand. Most residents of that country speak English. Scientists believe that today there are 1,494,010 English words. According to the classification, this language is part of a family of flexible languages.

It is estimated that a total of about 30 million people speak Uzbek in Uzbekistan, Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Turkey. His vocabulary ranges

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from 120,000 to 220,000 words, according to various sources. Depending on the typological nature of the Uzbek language, it is an agglutinative language.

Several translation transformations will have to be used to convert text written in a flexible type of language into agglutinative type text. First, the vocabulary of the languages that enter the contact does not correspond in quantity to each other, The second is the validity of forming vocabulary, which, predictably, differs from one another. When you look at languages grammatically and lexically, the vocabulary of the two languages and the word categories do not coincide. In addition, the explicit and implicit meanings of words, words with additional meaning, and special words (national words, realia) differ in the two languages. These listed characteristics require the usage of phonetic, linguistic, grammatical, linguistic, and semantic transformations in translations.

Wherever this translation observes incompatibility in language units (phoneme, morpheme, word, word combination, phrase, and text), it is required to apply transformation here. (Some scholars also include the text among language units. Their main argument is that because the sentence consists of words, the word consists of morphemes and morphemes contain phonemes, text is recognized as the largest language unit because the text is divided into sentences, words, phrases, and so on. However, this idea is not supported by most scientists.)

The most common and the most widely used transformation is a change in word order. This type of transformation occurs at every step of the translation process.

Translation transformations include adding a word that serves as the basis for transformation in translation, as well as dropping, generalizing, concreting, calculating, and visual translation methods. The fact that the number of transformations is small indicates that languages are close to each other and that the large number of transformations denotes that the languages are far from each other.

The proper use of translation transformations in the appropriate place will be an important issue for translation science—the preservation of translation content as fully as possible. The full preservation of the translation content ensures its viability and, as a result, its quality is high.

There are four important approaches to translation. These include linguistic, cultural, pragmatic, and sociolinguistic approaches. In the process of translation, these can be theoretically distinguished. In practice, however, these cannot be distinguished from each other because they come together with each other and serve to fill each other. In fact, based on the above-mentioned approaches, taking into account their principles ensures the adequacy of translation by determining the extralinguistic factors of translation.

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